

This template was developed to support the preparation of structured, transparent, and reproducible economic analysis plans.

Instructions for Use: Replace the fields in brackets. Remove non-applicable sections. Define analytical decisions a priori whenever possible.

Version Control: V x.x.

Project Title: [Insert the study title, identifying the intervention and the at-risk population]

Responsible Team: [Names of the student team and supervising professor]

Date and Version: [e.g., October, 2025 – Version 1]

1. INTRODUCTION AND GOVERNANCE

Health Problem: [Describe the oral condition (e.g., caries) and the need for evaluation in the clinical or public policy context]

Scientific Evidence (Background or Rationale): [Present the evidence synthesis or theoretical justification supporting the use of the technologies analyzed (e.g., GRADE-based reviews or minimal intervention protocols)]

Economic Question: [Formulate the central evaluation question (e.g., Which fluoride application strategy is more cost-effective for the SUS in high-risk patients?)]

Conflict of Interest and Funding: [Declare funding sources and detail how independence of results and transparency were ensured]

2. STUDY DESIGN

[Customization – Select the appropriate option for your project]:

Content developed for the course Health Economics Applied to Dentistry, under the supervision of the Center for Evidence and Economic Evaluations, FOUSS (NEPAE_USP) and the EviDent initiative for training and capacity building of stakeholders involved in the process.

Recommended Citation: Braga MM, Cavalcanti Y, Fernandes AFC, Carrer FCA, Machado GM, Pannutti CM, Pontes LRA on behalf of NEPAE, EviDent groups, TAPAS-HEAP: Template for Economic Analysis Plans in Health Studies. 2026. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.1935608](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1935608). License: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

() **Economic Evaluation Nested in a Clinical Trial:** [Use of primary data collected directly from a trial or clinical study conducted by the team]

() **Model-Based Evaluation:** [Use of mathematical models to simulate outcomes based on efficacy data extracted from the literature]

() **Other Design:** [Describe if the study is cohort, observational, or another type]

3. METHODS AND SCOPE

Population (Base Cases): [Define patient profiles (age, dentition, risk) representing the base cases of the analysis]

Setting and Location: [Specify the healthcare system context where the intervention takes place (e.g., Primary Care in SUS)]

Interventions and Comparators: [List the main interventions and controls used in the primary studies]

Perspective: [Define the analytical perspective (e.g., Healthcare Provider – SUS)]

Time Horizon: [Determine the follow-up period required to observe outcomes (e.g., 2-year cycles or until exfoliation)]

4. MODELING STRUCTURE (If applicable)

Type of Model: [Specify whether a Decision Tree, Markov Model, or other will be used]

Health States: [Define transition states of the tooth or patient (e.g., Healthy, Cavity, Restored, Extracted)]

Model Validation: [Describe how assumptions and structure will be validated (e.g., expert consultation or comparison with previous studies)]

5. COSTS AND EFFECTS

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5.1 Cost Estimation

Cost Items: [Identify resources: infrastructure, instruments, materials, personnel, and maintenance]

Valuation Source: [Indicate where prices come from (e.g., government price databases, validated repositories, or supplier quotations)]

Currency and Discounting: [Indicate the currency (BRL), PPP conversion, and applied discount rate (standard 5%)]

5.2 Effects and Valuation

Outcome Measure: [Define clinical or utility indices used (e.g., DMFT, surfaces saved, QALYs)]

Effect Valuation (for Cost-Benefit): [If conducting cost-benefit analysis, describe how the effect will be monetized, citing the Willingness to Pay (WTP) source and adjustment indices such as IPCA]

6. ANALYTICAL STRATEGY AND UNCERTAINTY

Primary Metric: [Define the main outcome indicator, usually the Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER)]

Sensitivity Analysis:

- **Deterministic (One-way):** [Indicate which variables will be varied individually to test robustness (e.g., costs $\pm 25\%$, effects $\pm 10\%$)]
- **Probabilistic (PSA):** [Describe the use of probability distributions and number of simulations (e.g., 10,000)]

Heterogeneity: [Plan subgroup analyses, if feasible (e.g., by caries risk, income, or tooth type)]

Software: [List programs to be used for calculations and simulations]

7. RESULTS AND DISSEMINATION

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Presentation Plan: [Indicate how data will be displayed (e.g., cost-effectiveness plane, acceptability curves)]

Engagement and Deliberative Dialogue: [Describe how results will be discussed with policymakers, professionals, and civil society]

Generalizability: [Discuss transferability of findings to other contexts or healthcare systems]

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